

Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: The importance of principals' leadership practices in teacher performance is interesting to study. The purpose of this literature is to analyze the principal's leadership practices in teacher performance. The articles used in this literature review were obtained using the Google Scholar database by entering the keyword "leadership leadership". There is some literature on principals' leadership in teacher performance found. Results Based on a literature study from various countries in the world, it was found that the principal's leadership style can improve teacher performance and can increase teacher commitment to the organization.

KEYWORDS: Leadership, Principal, Teacher Performance

INTRODUCTION

Global problems are engulfing various countries in the world along with the emergence of the Covid-19 outbreak until it eventually became a pandemic. Various regions in Indonesia have also been affected by the Covid-19 pandemic and have affected all sectors in society, including the education sector. The education sector must be able to face this pandemic so that learning activities can run. To break the chain of the spread of Covid-19, learning activities in schools are finally carried out online (in a network). This online learning activity is expected to affect teacher performance in teaching. There are many challenges that require teachers to master them in learning activities during this Covid-19 pandemic. During this pandemic period, many schools implemented online learning activities, including SMP Negeri 1 Purbolinggo

1. As per the circular of the Minister of Education and Culture (Hasan, 2021)

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the learning process was carried out at home through online learning to break the chain of the spread of COVID-19. All Students and Teachers study from home, which is suddenly done without any preparation. The unpreparedness of all elements in education is a big obstacle too, a change in the way of teaching and learning from face-to-face to online requires the readiness of all elements, starting from the government, schools, teachers, students and parents. (Russamsi, Yunus; Et. Al, 2020). The success of the educational process is largely determined by the ability of the education leader himself in the school scope, which is the principal, this is in line with Mulyasa's opinion (Imansyah, 2020) educational leadership related to the problem of principals in increasing opportunities to hold meetings effectively with teachers in conducive situation. The behavior of the principal must be able to encourage the performance of the teachers, by showing a friendly, close and considerate feeling toward the teachers, both as individuals and as a group.

LITERATUR REVIEW

Teacher Performance

The quality of teacher performance will greatly determine the quality of educational outcomes, because teachers are the party most in direct contact with students in the learning process at school educational institutions. The teacher is basically one of the components in the learning process that plays a role in the formation of potential human resources in the field of development. As a component in the field of education, a teacher must participate actively and place his position as a professional, in accordance with the demands of a growing society, so that he is required to have integrity, loyalty, dedication, and responsibility to realize himself as a professional teacher (Russamsi, Yunus; Et. Al, 2020).

One of the educational problems faced by the Indonesian nation today is the low quality of education at every level and unit of education, especially primary and secondary education. The Education Director of the National Development Planning and Development Agency (Bappenas) said that based on 2011 United Nations Development Program (UNDP) data, Indonesia's education level index is still considered low at 14.6%, in contrast to Singapore and Malaysia which already have a better education level index.

namely 28% and 33%. The low quality of education in Indonesia will weaken Indonesia's competitiveness in facing the 2015 ASEAN economic community (Purwanto, Agus. Et. Al,2020).

According to Sari et al (2017) in their research entitled "The Influence of the Principal's Leadership Role and the Role of School Committees on the performance of Public Elementary School Teachers in Bandar Lampung" shows that the principal's leadership role and the school committee's role together have a significant effect on teacher performance, this can be seen from Field research with a 93.2% contribution means that if the principal's leadership is carried out well and the school committee is carried out with good teacher performance, it will also increase (Imansyah,2020).

Teacher performance is a barometer of the quality of education services in an education organization. The quality of the school itself is influenced by the principal's leadership factor, resulting in an increase in teacher performance. Therefore, the leadership of the principal is an influential factor in improving teacher performance. Based on this description, this study aims to determine the influence of the Principal Leadership of SMP Negeri 1 on teacher performance during the Covid-19 pandemic.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a literature review method. an article obtained from the google scholar site with the keywords principal leadership and teacher performance in both schools and universities.

To measure the principal's leadership variable, it is taken from the roles and functions of the principal, including as Educator, Manager, Administrator, Supervisor, Leader, Innovator, and Motivator (EMASLIM). The teacher performance variable is measured based on the teacher performance assessment made by the Ministry of National Education, namely planning, implementing, and evaluating (assessing) learning activities that are adapted to conditions during the Covid- 19 pandemic.

Table 1. Criteria for Inclusion and Exclusion

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Principal Leadership	Paper, Essay, Thesis
Transformational Leadership	Company, Hospital
Teacher Performance	
Last 10 years article	

RESULT

The following presents the results of the literature review that the author has done. The results obtained focus on transformational leadership on teacher performance, both within the scope of schools and universities. The articles obtained are not only from Indonesia, but from various countries with various respondents. The results of the literature review that the author has done will be shown in the table below:

Table 2. Results of Literature Review

Title	Author(s) and Year	Type of Organization	of N	Country	Method	Result
The influence of principals Leadership, Academic Supervision, and Professional Competense toward Teachers' performance	Dewi Kartini, Muhammad Kristiawan, Happy Fitria (2020)	School	128 teachers	Indonesia	Quantitative research	The results of study suggest that teacher performance will be more professional if balanced with routine and structured academic supervision services for school principals as quality school culture.

Manajemen science letters	Sitti Hartinah, Putut Suharto, Rofiqul Umam, Muhamad Syazali, Bella Dwi Lestari, Roslina and Kittisak Jermisittipars ert (2020)	School	300 Quisioner	Indonesia	Quantitative research	Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the principal, work environ-ment, and motivation to affiliate are well perceived by the teachers.
Kebijakan Pendidikan di Indonesia	Abdul Rozak (2021)	School	-	Indonesia	Qualitative research	The policy implementation process only begins when the originally general goals and objectives have been planned, programs have been designed and a budget has been allocated to realize these goals and objection of the education policy of the Autonomy Era is still not clearly formatted, so in the field there are still various methods and methods of implementing education quality improvement programs. Therefore, the existing rules and quidelines need to be reviewed so as to lead to policy making in term of implementation.
Kebijakan Pendidikan dalam Kebijakan Publik	Hamidah D (2020)	School	-	Indonesia	Doctrinal (normative)	The Foundation of Public Policy in Education Policy It is a necessity for educational scientists, especially educational administration scientists to understand the study of public policy (public policy), especially educational policy (educational policy).

The impact of principal leadership styles on teacher job satisfaction and student success	Michael Baptiste (2019)	School	722 teachers	Indonesia	Literature review	Principal leadership plays a significant role in determining the experiences of teachers, the experiences of students, and the overall school climate.
Effect of Educator Qualification on Educational Institutions	Imam Tabroni, Alvioni Nadea Fikriah, Dida Nurbaida, Fadilah Qoulan Sadida (2022)	School	-	Indonesia	Qualitative research	Education is a conscious or unconscious effort of every element of education to instill good moral values or character in students. With the limited knowledge of an educator because they do not have the exact same skills as a teacher who has a bachelor's degree. In contrast to teachers who have not yet graduated, they may lack an understanding of how to know the characteristics of children, lack of understanding when dealing with children who experience tantrums at school.

DISCUSSION

A. Transformational Leadership and Motivation

The concept of transformational leadership is one of the most significant leadership models put forward in relation to the advancement of the educational field (Hallinger, 2003). In education, studies suggest that transformational leadership has an effect on teachers' commitment and on their attitudes toward their jobs (Hallinger, 2003). The term transformational leadership was coined by Bass (1985), referring to a theory that is considered one of the most popular theories among the various inspirational theories of leadership (Yaslioglu & SelenayErden, 2018). According to Bass and Avolio (1993), the four domains of transformational leadership are: (a) charisma or idealized influence, (b) inspirational motivation, (c) intellectual stimulation, and (d) individualized consideration. These notions are built upon the proposition that transformational leadership is a more effective form of leadership than transactional leadership (Bass & Avolio, 1993). Avolio & Yammarino (2013) refer to idealized influence as behavioral charisma. In this context, leaders strive to gain trust, loyalty, admiration, and respect from the teachers on their staffs through the application of a charismatic vision and through leading by example. The dimension of idealized influence demands that the principal lead by example, act confidently with optimism, share risks associated with the application of theories, and reinforce values through a high level of ethical behavior (Alzoraiki, Rahman, & Mutalib, 2018). Principals that lead with idealized influence instill a sense of faith for a better future in all members of their organizations, including the students (Berson & Oreg, 2016).

B. Leadership in the Educational Context The leadership

Behaviors of principals can influence teachers' experiences and work lives (Ch, Ahmad, Malik, & Batool, 2017; Kars & Inandi, 2018; Rana, Malik, & Hussain, 2016). The leadership behaviors of principals have been found to be intimately linked to teachers' sense of self-efficacy (Mehdinezhad & Mansouri, 2016), which could have a long-lasting effect on teachers' overall job performance and organizational commitment. For instance, in a study focused on school principals' leadership behaviors and teachers' organizational trust, Kars and Inandi (2018) concluded that principals carry the feelings of trust among teachers. While there is not a universal definition of trust, Cook and Wall (1980) laid out a frequently used definition of trust as "the extent to which one is willing to ascribe good intentions to, and have confidence in, the words and actions of other people" (p. 39). When there is trust in the workplace, teachers are less hesitant to share ideas with other teachers and their leader (Shih, Chiang, & Chen, 2012). Kars and Inandi (2018) investigated the link between school principals' leadership behaviors and teachers' organizational trust and explored whether leadership behaviors can significantly predict the dimensions of teachers' organizational trust and job satisfaction. A total of 722 participated in the correlational survey study, identifying three dimensions of organizational trust – principal trust, trust in colleagues, and trust in students and parents (Kars & Inandi, 2018). Findings showed that democratic leadership behaviors had a positive and significant relationship to all dimensions of organizational trust, while autocratic and laissez-faire leadership behaviors were negatively associated with all dimensions of organizational trust (Kars & Inandi, 2018). Kars and Inandi (2018) also found that democratic leadership behaviors were the strongest predictors of principal trust.

Zeinabadi and Rastegarpour (2010) conducted a quantitative research study of 652 primary school teachers in Iran, examining the relationships among the factors of transformational leadership style, job satisfaction, and trust with the principal. Results indicated a positive relationship between transformational leadership style and trust between the teachers and the principal (Zeinabadi & Rastegarpour, 2010). The results affirmed the finding of Kars & Inandi (2018) that trust is a central component to organizational success and teacher job satisfaction. Ch et al. (2017) studied the association between principals' leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction. A total of 200 teachers were randomly selected to answer a questionnaire that focused on questions about demographic variables, principals' leadership styles (autocratic and democratic), and job satisfaction (Ch et al., 2017). Based on the Pearson's analysis, Ch et al. (2017) concluded that most of the principals used a democratic type of leadership, as reflected by their efforts to take suggestions from teachers and the cooperation and support they provided to teachers. However, the operational goals and policies of the schools were determined primarily by the principals (Ch et al., 2017). Study findings also revealed that democratic leadership was significantly linked to teachers' job satisfaction. Thus, Ch et al. (2017) argued that principals are tasked with improving the participation of teachers in the decision-making processes of school communities. Rana et al. (2016) investigated the impact of perceived positive leadership styles (i.e., transformational and transactional leadership) on teachers' job involvement. A total of 250 public and private teachers responded to items on the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire and Job Involvement Scale (Rana et al., 2016). Findings demonstrated that transactional and transformational styles and their subscales were significantly and positively related to job involvement (Rana et al., 2016). Furthermore, Rana et al. (2016) found that idealized influence and intellectual stimulation, both sub-facets of transformational leadership, were predictive of job involvement.

CONCLUSION

The literature on leadership reflects the dynamic role of leaders in various contexts (Al-Abaneh, 2013; Fiaz et al., 2017; Solà, Badia, Delgado Hito, Campo Osaba, & Del Val García, 2016; Sahoo & Dash, 2017). Although transactional and transformational leadership styles are both related to the motivation of the followers, it is important to note that transactional leadership entails an exchange of something of value, while transformational leadership has been shown to nurture involvement and shared commitments to greater goals (Burns, 1978; Yaslioglu & Selenay Erden, 2018). The behaviors of school leaders profoundly impact the experiences of the teachers as well as the overall performance of the school. Principal leadership plays a significant role in determining the experiences of teachers, the experiences of students, and the overall school climate. Previous research has shown that principals can influence teacher job satisfaction and work performance and can impact student performance (Ch et al., 2017; Kars & Inandi, 2018; Mehdinezhad & Mansouri, 2016; Rana et al., 2016). Studies focusing on the experiences of principals emphasize the perceived characteristics of school leaders, including the ability to understand the politics of their positions and their capacity for meeting the expectations of the community (Hansen, 2018; Beam, Russell, Claxton, & Smith, 2016). Furthermore, it is critical for principals to receive professional support and training from experienced school leaders.

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